

Idea Challenge e-learning

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Pedagógusok Egyesülete

Entrepreneurial thinking

Startup Ecosystem /
Becoming a Startupper

Innovative leaders and entrepreneurs know that "Soft Skills" are the hardest to master, but the most important for their business. Soft Skills are the skills, habits and behaviors that differentiate us as professionals and make the difference in our ability to achieve a project goal, resolve conflict and interact with others.

Knowledge and practice in leadership, efficiency, team management, sales and communication skills are among the most valuable tools for entrepreneurs.

The importance of Soft Skills for entrepreneurs

Startup Ecosystem/Becoming a Startupper

The ability to start new businesses, especially start-ups based on innovative elements, requires the continuous learning and development of these skills (EU principle of life long learning). This is a necessary approach to be able to continuously build and develop our projects. Just as it is not enough that the business plan prepared at the beginning does not hold up to the constant changes and challenges, so in self-development and self-learning, the entrepreneur needs something more if he wants to be successful.

Every day we add new knowledge to our "baggage", but it is important to have the best soft skills from the starting point that will help us develop our project, make us a credible and effective leader in our team. We need a synthesis of the classic leadership skills - such as autonomy, accountability, critical vision - and the integration of the soft-skills that are more prominent in the startup ecosystem - credibility, accountability, resilience.

Training exercise: Individual competition: what is your idea? After this, we can make a teamwork exercise: brainstorming to make better ideas.

Tools for the exercise: First of all, you'll need a Genially account. Website: <https://app.genial.ly>.

Make your own Genially account. Step to Creations menu point. After step to Interactive Images menu point: <https://app.genial.ly/templates/interactive-image>

If you are ready, make a word -cloud about your idea. Use the key words in your marketing and business strategy. As an entrepreneur, businessman or manager, you need a local and global network. This is the startup ecosystem

Training exercise 2. :

Test in Genially:

What are the parts of the perfect startup ecosystem. You can collect the parts, for example: university, coworking, makerspace, venture capital, incubator, mentors, etc.

After you can make a presentation about this with Genially: <https://app.genial.ly/templates/presentation>

Developing our skills

Creativity and brainstorming

The entrepreneur or startupper must be aware of these rules and be ready to develop our soft skills needed in this area in a continuous and variable way. However, this alone is not sufficient if one of the most important of these skills, the managerial approach, does not underpin this whole process and if it does not receive sufficient attention and energy to nurture and strengthen it.

It is worth taking a critical look at aspects and content of the classic literature on managerial thinking, as user habits and customer expectations (UX/UI perspective) have changed in recent timecap, both in terms of the social image of service providers and their personal or corporate social responsibility.

Idea and idea brainstorming

In any innovation process or in the life of a work organisation, one of the important elements of progress is the identification, management and solution of problems. Today, in Anglo-Saxon business culture, one of the most important skills expected of intellectual workers and employees is problem-solving - and for good reason.

There are several different definitions of problem solving, let's look at a few of them:

The definition of a problem according to the Kaizen concept: the difference between the ideal state and the current state. Any question or task for which the answer - the solution - cannot be found immediately and precisely.

According to Mayer (1977): important elements in the definition of a problem are that they occur in a certain state, a different state is desirable, there is no or no known direct, obvious way to solve it.

To sum up, we can say that we speak of a problem when we have a task to be solved or a state - more ideal than the present one - that we want to achieve, but we do not know how to do it, we do not know the way to achieve it. The process of finding and developing a solution is called problem solving.

Creative problem solving techniques

Today, the teaching and development of better thinking and creative, problem-solving thinking is a significant part of primary and secondary education in Hungary. According to research on creativity, there is a good chance that we will lose 90% of our built-in creativity by the time we reach adulthood. This is why the importance of creative thinking techniques that can be learned outside schools is invaluable. If we want to regain our lost creativity, let's learn to think creatively in a systematic way.

The most common symptoms of flawed problem-solving thinking are an incomplete, one-sided perspective, a 'I'm right, you're wrong' attitude, instant criticism, and a search for conventional, foolproof methods. This is coupled with a lack of organisation and management of work processes. Random, haphazard methods are usually used to solve problems. In contrast, controlled, creative problem-solving methods are different, based on a set of solution paths. Specificities and tools are strong visuality, which is effective because it is an ancient mode of our thinking brain. We call these methods regulated because they are structured processes between problem definition and solution. The methods have a fixed sequence of phases, nothing can be left out or changed, and a set framework and techniques are necessary to be effective.

And the techniques are creative because:

- they are characterised by divergence rather than convergence
- they are multi-directional and branched rather than linear
- they generate multiple ideas rather than a single solution
- they provide more opportunities for original solutions
- they engage both hemispheres of your brain

A hypothesis in a form that can be proved or disproved by experimental methods and data collection.

Hypothesis: in science, a principle or proposition that is consistent with experience and explained by observed facts, but lacks proof. We have a new hypothesis about the origin of man", "We are dependent on hypotheses until we find conclusive evidence".

The idea you have chosen is based on a hypothesis that you have formed from studying the immediate environment.

The first and most important task is to test this hypothesis, in startup terms - to validate your idea.

At first, everything is just a hypothesis.

It is important to make it clear that the idea is initially a hypothesis, even if it seems perfectly logical and plausible at first. From then on, its marketability is assured if it has been tested and you can clearly see the reaction of the prospective target group when they encounter the product. People react differently to a product when you just imagine what it would be like than when they actually get their hands on it. The actual market testing of an idea or hypothesis is called validation.

Think about the idea in a nutshell and write it down in a few sentences! Formulate the hypothesis.

Training exercise: What was the moment, the motivation that made them think they would invest time, energy and money in this. Make them aware that it will be important to recall these thoughts and feelings in future challenges, because they will help them overcome the difficulties. This exercise is the first step to practising presenting their thoughts, preparing them for the challenges of presenting a pitch of early stage ideas.

Tools for the exercise: speaking with AI (chatGPT) about your idea, and hypothesis. Questions for AI what do you think about my business idea? I have competitors whole of the world? My target group is real?

Write 5-10 questions for AI about your business idea and theory.

Entrepreneurial skills - Soft Skills

We will summarise the soft skills that are most important for the entrepreneur and develop them in relation to the areas that are most relevant for startups. It's not about becoming perfect in one area and then moving on to the next, but rather about having the right mix of the important elements, for example : presentation on communication skills, networking culture, and prepare methods.

Soft skills for startupper

One of the most important elements related to this area is initiative. Being proactive is a complex concept and can be interpreted in many different ways. It means understanding new industrial trends, their market potential and product market fit, being flexible in new situations, coordinating resources and team members, and using innovative methods to implement to our company. Continuous training, self-education, training courses and further education are among the most important things for entrepreneurs. Taking the initiative is essential to take the first step, to start a new business or to launch an idea. Without this creative and problem solving soft skill, it is very difficult to become an entrepreneur.

Without sales, investors, partners, and other startup ecosystem members there is no business and to be effective in these we need to negotiate in countless ways and times. It is also true that methods, trends and tendencies are changing dynamically. Not only do the channels of communication evolve on an almost daily basis, but so do the rules of business etiquette, including, for example, business dress, and customs. The emergence and prominence of online or offline pitches, social media platforms and blockchain or AI technology, the use of which must be taken into account, but also the traditional methods, values and soft skills.

The use of communications and networking skills has changed and is changing a lot today. Personal networking systems are forcing entrepreneurs to rethink their approach with the proliferation of social media, Web 2 applications. The self branding is a very important thing in these days. However, it is also true here that the classic methods cannot be forgotten, and that the rules of personal contact and persuasive behaviour must be learned and practised. This includes good communication - including meta, verbal, non-verbal areas - and knowledge of the rules of dress, respect for social - and culture-dependent - etiquette. At the same time, online channels and social spaces have developed their own set of rules and regulations, which, because of their differences, have made this area even more complex.

Networking means expanding the professional network of contacts, and without contacts without networking there is no business, and this is true even if the changing tools and platforms give the impression that it can be left out of the process or completely automated. Networking events continue to be an important element in the development of our business, and here too the mosaic of change across age groups, cultures, countries and many other factors is of particular importance.

The entrepreneur must be aware of the importance of effective communication as a crucial element of business strategy and competitiveness improvement, which has a major impact on all other activities and even on other soft skills. To make our communication effective and to be able to continuously improve, we need to develop a more comprehensive vision. Here too, the dynamics of our social and business environment are such that we must occasionally rely on our own intuition as to what might be the most effective method in the current situation. An important part of communication is the ability to address people effectively. The entrepreneur must have people management skills, in a positive sense. You need to be able to identify the needs of your customers and your team, your company, to choose the most appropriate staff to work with, to decide which of the investment opportunities to accept, who to vote for.

Training exercise: Internet research to collect from participants what combination of skills characterizes well-known leaders (Elon Musk, Steve Jobs, etc.), how they are reflected in the implementation of their ideas, in their businesses, in the material they are seen with. After the research make a summary in genially.

Use the infographics topic : <https://app.genial.ly/templates/infographics>

Tools for the exercise: smart phone or laptop, wi-fi connection

Creativity and change management

Flexibility and change management skills:

Effective change management will make all the difference for entrepreneurs who want to thrive in the 2020s business environment, adaptability is an important key to success. It can be said that the practical implementation of true self-reliance in our business is a leadership style that represents a level of commitment and the forms of communication that respond to the "here and now", that is the ability to reinvent.

Creativity and visionary skills: is needed because starting from an idea, from "nothing" and even with little to "no money", it takes imagination in every detail to start working towards your goals. In addition, changes in practice require a lot of imagination to face up to the various unexpected challenges that may arise. There is a particular value in someone who can add value to their project, someone who can make an attention-grabbing proposal, someone who can think in alternative ways to the usual, and who can be enthusiastic about it and infect others with this drive.

Creativity in the world of startups is best described as "Think outside the box", so that we don't just think in terms of design. This business English slang term is not used here primarily in its original meaning, thinking outside the box means coming up with new ideas, using new approaches, seeing things differently from others.

Training exercise: The task is to come up with marketing ideas for the "Giovanni's" spaghetti factory. The factory offers a 1.5 km long but only 30 cm wide piece of land for the campaign. The task of the participants is to use this land in as many ways as possible to present and promote the spaghetti factory, using as many creative solutions as possible. The participants will write down the ideas they have collected on geniallyt, The AI gave a feedback from the data base.

Tools for the exercise: genially, the gamification topic. <https://app.genial.ly/templates/games>

If planning and organization emerge as a competence, do not confuse busyness with productivity and efficiency. Everyone has had experiences of spending days intensively working, writing or going from meeting to meeting, but at the end of the day feeling that they had not achieved any real results. It's easy to fall into this trap and that's why it's so important to work on your personal productivity, to be able to optimize the use of your time, energy and activities.

There are a number of soft skills that support planning and organization, but it is worth analyzing strategic, analytical, and conceptual thinking.

The ability to think strategically or to orientate takes on significance when we talk about the need for entrepreneurs and organizations to maintain a dynamic environment by developing and following continuous strategic change. It comes to the fore when their survival depends on their ability to innovate their models, to rethink flexible responses to market forces.

As this is primarily a people-dependent process, entrepreneurs are the drivers of the change process, they are the ones who make strategic decisions based on their beliefs, their perceptions of the economic and social environment, their business portfolio and the state of the organization.

Analytical thinking is the ability to understand and solve situations, to solve problems by breaking down their components in a logical and systematic way. It is this technique, this type of thinking, that makes it possible to improve the quality of analysis in any aspect of any professional activity, providing those who use it with an advantage that is visible in the effectiveness of the results achieved. They are also a quick and efficient way to improve our agenda and time management.

Overview or Conceptual thinking is the application of creative, conceptual or inductive reasoning to existing concepts or to define new concepts. Conceptual thinking is understanding a situation or problem by putting the pieces together to determine to establish completeness.

Learning from feedback

For innovative, new products and services, it is important to get user feedback and incorporate it into the business. The UX/UI approach and the user feedback loop are important from the first phase of product development. When the product is already on the market but new options are added to the product portfolio, the feedback loop should be repeated. It is a never-ending workflow.

Positive or constructive user feedback should be incorporated. Negative reviews should also be considered and dealt with in the appropriate place. An important question is who, when and how to give feedback. Methodologically, feedback forms can be in online and offline formats. For example, there is a big difference between a short online questionnaire and a face-to-face focus group interview. With the right critical thinking and a user-friendly approach, we can use feedback to our advantage.

Training exercise: Participants, present their business ideas to genially, and ask for feedback. The "salesperson" makes a presentation with geniallyt, The AI, as a "buyer" tries to give constructive criticism of the product.

Tools for the exercise: any online platform, for example google meets, zoom, etc. and genially

Confidence can be the key to entrepreneurial success! If you are confident in yourself, your team, your idea and your ability to achieve the goals you have set, you can really show this to investors, customers and communities. When we talk about being able to build confidence, it means that you believe that everything will work out, that despite the fact that there is room for error and success is the most likely outcome. Confidence is self-control, without self-discipline you can easily collapse, break momentum and become discredited. You need to be able to adapt to changing environments and challenges in times of difficulty, to be able to withstand adversity. The increasingly common term in this context is resilience.

In psychological terms, resilience is the ability of a person to recover quickly from unexpected, stressful or difficult life situations, or physical and mental suffering. One of the most important capacities of the twenty-first century human being, its importance cannot be overestimated when we talk about maintaining or improving mental health, coping with and recovering from difficult situations in life.

"It's not what competences you have, but how you combine them"

A potential entrepreneur needs to combine courage with openness, while being able to cope well with the pressures that come his way. How do the soft skills needed for entrepreneurship differ from the managerial competences essential in a corporate - "multinational" - environment? Many popular training materials and podcasts by influencers talk in general about the soft skills needed to lead people, manage clients, negotiate, and the importance of developing them. It's important to distinguish how it's different if you have to start, manage and develop your own business.

Training exercise: Create an online questionnaire about your prospective product, using an online platform such as google forms or typeform. Include 5-10 questions, both multiple choice and multiple choice. Try to get it out to as many people as possible through online platforms such as Facebook groups. Evaluate the answers and make notes.

Tools for the exercise: typeform or googlesheet or genially quiz topic <https://app.genial.ly/templates/games>

We've already seen why being a credible, transparent person is important for your product or service and why it's a key factor for successful and challenged leaders today.

An entrepreneur, start-up or idea implementer must be prepared to be a leader for his or her employees. As this aspect has already been raised, it is important to be aware of how you will be able to handle this situation. A manager at the end of the first quarter of the 21st century should be a leader, not a boss, knowing that the more his employees trust him, the more they like him and the more likely they are to want to work for him. A leader does not want to be someone who forces employees to work, but someone who empowers them, who gives them a reason to work other than a salary. He wants to make sure that his employees know that he is trying to make a difference and that as a team they can achieve great things. Be their leader, not someone who bosses them around.

The competency to master learning is increasingly important for an entrepreneur and startupper because of the ever-changing challenges. You need an ever-renewing technical knowledge base with a focus on selling.

Innovation - Organizational skills

Business planning

Millions of people are thinking about which option would be worth pursuing, they keep coming up with ideas, but the key difference is which one will be successful in implementation. Which one of an entrepreneur's own ideas or those of others ancestors can be implemented is based on talent and training. "An idea, from an entrepreneurial perspective, is a business idea to produce products or provide services that can be sold in the market."

If you have a great idea, you need validation, feedback and business plan. You need to know, who is your customer. The Emphaty Map and the Business Model Canvas is good practice for this.

The customer

The Empathy Map and the Persona

Empathy Map - Theory

To (also) see and examine our value proposition and business model from the customer's perspective.

As small business owners, we cannot afford to use expensive marketing tools in vain, as this can easily lead to failure. But if we know who we want to reach, we can choose the most appropriate tools in a conscious and controlled way. We should give priority to those who we believe to be the most credible. Or because we are one of them, and because we share their problems and life situations (e.g. a coach turned mother who has followed the path they are advising on. Or because we have a wealth of references and indisputable knowledge on a particular subject.

If we approach the target group from our own strengths and find those whose needs we can meet, we are on the right track. On this basis, it is recommended to select two or three teams, but no more than five, who can be described in detail.

In this context, it is important to stress that our communication is never about us! Messages must always be formulated for the target group (we put ourselves in their shoes), using the language and communication channels they know.

If you know your target group's habits, you know which online-offline and direct-indirect channels to use to reach them. It is useful to think about questions such as: what events they go to, what media they consume, where and how they go to work, what they eat, what they drink, etc. The answer will give us a precise guide.

Themes of empathy map:

- What do you see?
- What do they hear?
- What do they think and feel?
- What does he hear?
- What does he hear? What does she do?

Training exercise.: make your own buyer persona with genially. You can use the templates, for example the Genial Bio in infographics menupoint.

Tools for the exercise: <https://app.genial.ly/templates/infographics>

Empathy Map

The empathy map is a great help here, because it allows the most in-depth analysis. On the basis of the empathy map, it is possible to examine what a member of the target group we have selected sees in the world around them, what they hear from others, what they think and feel about a topic in which we are working. The analysis will also give us an answer as to what pain points the person has on the issue in question and what would be of value, use or solution (pain - gain).

The main questions:

Demography aspects:

- what is the gender of my customer?
- how old is my user?
- what is the social status of my user
- how much income does my user have?
- what type of work does my user do?
- what is the hobby is my user?
- what is the relationship status of my user? (for example: married, single etc.)
- does my user have children?
- where is my user located? (for example: capitol city, small village etc.)
- does my user have house or flat?
- does my user have a car or other vehicle?

This set of questions gives an in-depth picture of the business's prospective customers.

Training exercise.: build your own empathy map

Tools for the exercise: Role and task cards, persona cards. Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers

Business planning basics and Business Model Canvas

The Business Model Canvas is a strategic management and lean startup method for developing and documenting the business model of existing or new companies.

The Business Model Canvas is a visual modelling tool. A 1-page template is used to place information relevant to the category. This is typically done in short, concise, few-word texts written on post-its.

Classical business plans are typically 30-70 page written documents that detail the business environment, strategy, competitors, assumptions and financial calculations related to the business model of the company or project.

In contrast, the Business Model Canvas presents the key building blocks of a project on a single page. This makes it a much quicker, simplified and schematic model to put together. However, this does not mean that it is inaccurate or wrong. It simply means that its purpose and value lies not in the detail, but in the basic context. If there is already a flaw in the relationship between the basic elements, it is completely pointless to write a 50-page business plan for that project. In this respect, the canvas is not a substitute for the business plan, but precedes and complements it. Think of it as an executive summary of a business plan.

The model consists of the following nine elements:

- Value Proposition
- Customer Segments
- Channels
- Customer Relationship
- Revenue Streams
- Cost Structure
- Key Activities
- Key Resources
- Partners

Business Model Canvas I.

The canvas model is an enhanced version of the Lean Business Model, it builds a business enterprise from 9 components that summarise briefly and concisely the aspects of the project's operation and strategy. As the name suggests, it is a model designed to represent complex real-world relationships in a simple, understandable way.

Advantages of the Business Model Canvas compared to other models

- it can be created quickly
- but can be extended in terms of content at any time
- it is flexible
- its simplicity and flexibility make it a popular choice for start-ups
- can even be used for non-profit initiatives

This model was also chosen because it can be used for non-profit initiatives. Participants' ideas are likely to include a programme that is not specifically for profit, but for community purposes.

Training exercise.: Participants working on their own ideas. Their task is to create three elements of a model based on the chosen idea:

- Define the relationship between the value proposition and the customer - Here they are looking for the answer to what value or product they are giving to the potential customer or target group.
- They plan the channels through which they will be able to connect them - The channel is responsible for how the customer will first interact with the product or service. And the customer connection is partly responsible for how the value will be delivered to them again and again.
- This will enable them to plan the source and frequency of access to the customer's money as a result of value creation.

Business Model Canvas II.

For startups, the term pivot is a well-known concept. The canvas side interpretation of pivot business model is quite simple: if one of the 9 elements of the model needs to be changed, it is a pivot.

This change can be a change in the value proposition. Or even to serve a new target group. Such a customer segment pivot. If, on the other hand, the revenue model changes from a one-off fixed-fee revenue model to a monthly fee pricing model, we can talk about a revenue model pivot.

The right side is the value-added, creative part. This includes value proposition, customer/target, channel, customer relationship and revenue. In other words, how we create value.

Just like the right side of the brain, which is responsible for the creative, value-creating tasks. In the business world this includes a company's marketing department, product development, business development.

In contrast, the left side of the canvas is responsible for rational, number-based decisions. It includes resources, activities, costs and partners. Just like finance, operations, controlling, IT and legal in a company.

And when there is a company debate about whether or not to launch a new project, similar questions tend to arise?

- Who is our target group, who are we selling to? (Client)
- What marketing channel will we use? (Channel)
- How will we make money from it? (Revenue)
- OK, who will do this? (Resource)
- How much will it cost? (Cost)
- What partners will we need to use if we can't do it in-house? (Partners)

So really the right and the left are fighting and struggling to balance each other. And hence, canvas is not only about value creation, creative side can be designed. Take a development company: they work for months on a project, and then when it runs out, there are a lot of free resources that management wants to do something with.

Training exercise: participants continue to work on the idea. Their task is to create the next three elements of the model for the selected idea:

- To produce value, you need to have resources to carry out the key activities, it is up to you to plan this.
- Engaging external partners to do the tasks if you cannot from the resources within the planned team. Benchmarking research will also be needed here to get an idea of possible service packages and their expected pricing.
- Planning the cost implications of the whole process. Balancing the items shown here with the revenue side to make it realistic to implement.

Value Proposition:

The main part of the BMC is the value proposition.

What is the value you create for the customer? What is my message to my customers?

The good value proposition is emotionally, clear and valuable.

The value proposition of the big companies we know today is usually linked to a sense of life or mission, rather than a specific product. For example: Nike - Just Do It , McDonalds - I'm lovin it , Apple - Be different. The value proposition is a clear mission statement for customers. The parts of value proposition: a logo, design, slogan, brandname etc.

If you want a good logo, brand or slogan, or creative commercial content, you can use the CHAT GPT or other AI app.

Training exercise:

As a idea owner , try to create your logo, your slogan and your first social media post. This is a creative practice. You can use online and offline tools for this.

If you are ready with this, show your creatives for the AI. The give feedbacks for you.

After this get your cell phone and make a free account in chat gpt (openai.com) website. After you can make a social media post or slogan with AI.

See and analysed what is the different between your and the Ai's work.

Minimum valuable product and onepager

How to make Minimum
Valuable Product?

After successful product validation, businesses will start building at least a valuable product. This is a low-cost, wireframe model of the prospective product. The aim is to allow potential users to test the product and give feedback to the idea creator. And the onepager is a visual, clean one-page summary of the project, including users, product market fit data, team profile and financials.

This is usually sent to investors and partners in the first round. In this module, we will learn the theoretical and practical background of onepager and Minimum Valuable Product (abbreviated MVP).

How to make Minimum Valuable Product?

After the MOM test and Validation

What is the MOM test? The MOM test is the philosophy of validation. Rob Fitzpatrick write a book about the validation, with this title. This is the Bible of validation in startup ecosystem.

Having a good idea is just the beginning. We need a validation process.

The first step is a market research and validation. We have many methods for this.

We can show six method for you, you can choose for a better for your own business.

1. Harvard Business School Market Research Method

Write Down Goals, Assumptions, and Hypotheses. The process of simply writing your thoughts down can lead to breakthroughs. Your goals can be defined, your assumptions examined, and your hypotheses tested. For example,:

what is the value of your product or offering?

Why are you different in a crowded marketplace?

What do you know about your business model?

More importantly, what don't you know? These may be difficult to answer but can save you time.

Assess Market Size and Share. How big is your market? Is there room for you to enter and take a piece of it? Conduct market research and see what is possible for your endeavor.

Research Search Volume of Related Terms. How can you tell if there is a need for your product or service? Simply see if your target customers are searching online for it. This is an easy way to test your hypothesis to determine if there is a demand.

Conduct Customer Validation Interviews. Talk to your potential customers. After all, they will have a general idea of what they want. Find out their needs, their problems, and their dream solution. Be open to feedback you receive.

Test Your Product or Service. There is a reason companies have alpha and beta versions of their products. This is to eliminate any bugs and workout any problems before the product is released into the market. Furthermore, you will learn what is working and what isn't.

2. Lean Market Validation

The lean market validation has more steps and is meant for rapidly testing a startup idea.

Write down the product concept. Write down assumptions that you can easily go out and test.

Decide. Get enough customer information and decide.

Realize that most of what you write down are assumptions. What you write down are not facts. In fact, most of your assumptions won't be used at all. The important part is to test your assumptions by getting started immediately.

Find the truth by testing your assumptions. Test your assumptions with your ideal customer type. Use a landing page or run inexpensive ads.

Start with your network. Use your network to reach your potential customers.

Interview your customers. Learn about your customers' pain points. Be curious about what they need and what you will gain valuable insights.

Ask, "Why?" By asking why, you can get to the underlying reason behind a customer's motivation.

Find the value proposition. This is extremely important. Why should the customer use your product or service? What does it help them do? Save time? Save money? Ease of use?

Understand that liking your idea is not the same as buying your product. Understand that people may want to be a supporter of your product or are just being friendly and enthusiastic to help you. As I always say, everyone is a gangster until they have to pull out a credit card.

Jump off the cliff and have fun. Take a chance on yourself and your idea. Have fun with the process

3. The Startup Grind Methodolo

The famous startup school and ecosystem builder organisation, the Startup Grind has a wonderful framework for validation that doesn't cost a single dollar.

Write down the problem, not the solution. Write down the problem you want to solve. Try to keep it to a simple statement.

Determine if the problem is tier 1. The problem you should be solving is one of the top problems your customers are facing. If the problem isn't one of the most pressing, then don't anticipate your customer to use it, let alone make a purchase.

Determine existing solutions. When talking to your potential customers, ask how they handle the problem with the current solutions available. If there aren't any solutions, that may be because there are too few people having this problem or the market doesn't exist.

Look for pain in existing solutions. What are the pain points when using specific solutions? What are they looking for to make their life easier? You need to have a unique benefit when it comes to your product compared to the competition.

Verify there's a budget for the solution. Examine your competitors. If they are growing, raising funds, or hiring, this is a good indication that customers are willing to pay for the product. Talk to your potential customers and see if they would pay for your product. Dig deep and find out why they would and more importantly, why they wouldn't.

Use your prospects to define your roadmap. Your prospects can give you feedback on your offering as you build out your MVP. In the best case scenario, they can become your first paying customers.

4. Arnab Ray's Startup Validation Framework

The famous Entrepreneur Arnab Ray came up with a simple graphic for startup validation. The goal of this framework is to provide a structured approach to founders that allow them to save on costs and analyze their ideas with the hope that they can understand the potential of their idea clearly. More importantly, the strengths, weaknesses, and risks are demonstrated.

5. The Failory 4-Step Framework

Define a pre-selling goal. What will validate your idea? How many sales will it take to convince you that the idea is validated? What is the time?

Build a minimum viable offer. The minimum viable offer can be a variety of different things. For some, it is a simple landing page. For others, it is a functional prototype. And it could even just be an explainer video.

Pre-sell your minimum viable offer. This can be done in a variety of ways. Leverage your audience via social media. Use forums and niche communities. Build in public. Guest post on blogs. Utilize Facebook and Google Ads. Whatever works best for you and your budget to get in front of your potential customers.

Analyze the results. Did you achieve your goal? If so, then the idea is validated. You can move forward with your business. If not, then you should quit while you still can. Refund any sales and let your customers know what happened.

SPD Load's Idea Validation Method

Define the why. The first step is defining the problem, the customer, and the innovation. Set validation goals. How many potential customers approve of your idea? If you are pitching companies, how many will give you a clear idea of success? How many successful sales or pre-orders will be relevant to you?

Formulate your hypothesis. What idea regarding your solution do you want to test? How can you prove it?

Create your value proposition. What makes you special? What benefits will your customers receive from the use of your product? Keep it simple so you can obtain feedback.

Validate. This could be everything from a single feature MVP to creating a landing page, blog, or explainer video.

Collect feedback. Are your customers happy? Was the feedback helpful? Or were the results less than stellar? What worked? What didn't?

Decide. Depending on your feedback, you can either stick with it or pivot. If you are building a product that provides real value, then you are onto something. If it didn't work, then the best choice may be to pivot and move on.

But how do you know if you are creating a product with real value? SPD Load also provides this handy checklist:

The right time for this product.

Having early adopters provide feedback.

Empathy. Finding out what the customer wants via their feedback.

Having a unique advantage over the competition.

Complexity. Simply ask if you are making your customers' lives easier.

Simplicity. The ability to explain your product in one clear sentence.

Conclusion, after the validation

Although all six validation frameworks we shared were different, they had common trends. When validating your startup idea, it is essential to write down your goals, have a relationship with your customer, experiment, and constantly listen to feedback to improve your offering.

We hope this article sets you on the path to validating your idea and arriving at not just an MVP, but a successful MVP that will be useful to your customers.

Training exercise: first of all, choose a market research method, after make your own market research. You can use the internet sources, and the Genially AI app can help you.

Training exercise II: make an MVP. Use online Genially platform for the exercise. The best menu point for this is the interactive pictures and videos, inside the Genially. <https://app.genial.ly/templates/interactive-image>

Onepager

Behind the onepager:

Today we will learn about and prepare the onepager.

The first step: talking about the onepagers background.

The onepager is a simple, transparent document that shows the startup's results, finances, product and needs in a clear and concise way. When creating the onepager, we use the results of the persona, market research and validation process.

You will see onepages on the screen, as an examples.

These are onepagers from a group of creative thinkers. Imagine that you are an investment manager and you have to decide whether to invite the idea manager for a face-to-face meeting based on the onepager. Please, everyone choose one!

Review and comment on the onepagers!

Group members will be given 5 minutes to study the onepagers they have chosen.

When you have thought about it and are ready, let's sit back in a big circle and each of you tell us your opinion about the onepager you have, as an investment professional who would you give the opportunity to meet in person and why?

Features of the onepager:

The onepager, as the name implies, is an one page size document. It follows a similar principle as an executive summary. Think of it as the name card of your company. Its purpose is to present the main elements of your startup in a concise and understandable way:

- the problem,
- the solution,
- the consumers,
- the target market,
- the competitors,
- the current
- current conditions,
- the product,
- the business model,
- the market entry strategy
- the need for investment

It is worthwhile to design the onepager aesthetically, It should be beautiful, transparent and clean.

What should be in the Onepager?

Problem/need

Most entrepreneurs start with the description or features of the space instead of talking about what really matters: what exactly is the j6? What does it solve?

In short: The problem/need. It is very important to be clear at the beginning exactly what problem you are focusing on, what you are trying to solve. Show clearly and concisely how the problem/need you have identified creates a business opportunity. You may take all this for granted, but this is not necessarily true for investors.

Questions to answer: How big is this problem? Whose problem are you solving?

Product/Service (the solution for problem)

After presenting the problem, the next step is to present the product/solution. Here you should present your product/solution as clearly as possible. Explain how your product/solution solves the problem/solution in the previous section, why it is useful and why there will be a demand for it.

The explanation and presentation should be understandable to both knowledgeable and less knowledgeable people.

If the physical appearance or other physical attributes of the product/service are an important part of a unique value proposition, it is worth presenting them in a picture, but the presentation should be clear and transparent.

Questions to answer: Why will it be in demand? What are its main features? Why are customers using it?

Target market and key users

After these questions, it is worth outlining the target market. Next, the current and potential future markets are presented. What is the size of the target market and what are the growth opportunities and directions. It is advisable at this point to present some graphs that will make it easy to understand the size, composition and sales potential of the market.

This will give the investor an immediate understanding of the short-term potential of your idea.

Don't make the mistake of focusing on a subordinate large market, instead of presenting a subordinate target market and talking about how that market will grow.

After presenting the market, talk about its users. Introduce your customers as if you know them as your own friends. Who is ok? What do they do? What do they do? What are their problems? What are their motivations to use your product? An investor appreciates working with a team that knows the market well and has invested the energy to get to know the user.

Questions: How big is the market? Who are your customers? What is your market size? Who is your target audience? How do you reach them?

Competitors and competitive advantage

In this section you show investors that you know your field really well. You need to be seen as an expert by your potential investors. To do this, you need to know the market well. Present your solution through a competitive prism, identify products that meet a similar need and show why your product is better.

Talk about your competitive advantage. Demonstrate that your product is better at the user, professional and business level. Demonstrate exactly what you are better at than your competitors and how you win the market.

Who are your competitors? What is your competitive advantage? What are your differentiators?

What are your competitive advantages?

Show how you currently position your company. Do you have a pipeline, what stage of development, how close are you to an MVP? In addition, if you already have all the erdeklodes for the halls/solution iran, please also elaborate on that. All this information will help to prove to the investor that it may be worth investing in the startup.

Don't make the mistake of focusing on a subordinate large market, instead of presenting a subordinate target market and talking about how that market will grow.

After presenting the market, talk about its users. Introduce your customers as if you know them as your own friends. Who is ok? What do they do? What do they do? What are their problems? What are their motivations to use your product? An investor appreciates working with a team that knows the market well and has invested the energy to get to know the user.

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What are your competitive advantages?

Business model

Present your business model: You are looking for an answer to the question of how your company will make money in a sustainable and scalable way.

What is the pricing strategy? How much does it cost to acquire a customer?

What is the market entry strategy?

Demonstrate your market entry strategy. How do you want to get your product to market?

Questions to answer: How do you plan to enter the market? What will be your main selling points? What are the main milestones for your market entry?

- What are the main market segments?

After these, present to the investor what you need and why!

How much money do you need? What do you need? How long will this amount last? What milestones do you want to achieve with this investor?

- How long do you want to invest?

The success of any business depends on the people working in it. Introduce the key people in your business and write a few lines about them. Stick to the basics, as examples: qualifications, previous experience and highlight the synergies of the team, how they complement each other's skills.

Try to avoid unnecessary information, most investors are not interested in your hobbies.

Who are the team members? What will make you the next startup success? What are you capable of doing to realise your company's vision? When did you start? What stage are you currently at? Where is the product development? What are your revenues?

Final steps:

- 1) Review the document from the perspective of an investor who is not familiar with the company. What are your greatest strengths as a startup? An innovative product? A new, unexplored market? Your experienced team? Your document should almost shout this strength to make the investor feel why you are the best.
- 2) On top of that, make sure it's neat, tidy and understandable. Check the internet for any information an investor might be after, such as domain, company details etc.
- 3) Look over the whole document again, correct any grammatical errors, typos and ask others to look at it. Print it out and see if it looks right, is readable, can be emailed.
- 4) Send it to friends and family who are not familiar with the market, the technology. See how they react, what they understand from the document.
- 5) If you were an investor, what other information would you ask for.

We looked at what a good one pager looks like from an investor's point of view. I also talked to you about the purpose of the onepager its role, content etc. Now let's each create our own idea of an onepager this is a first, general onepager to introduce products or services.

After the onepagers are made, the participants/teams can show them to each other and give feedback to each other as outside eyes.

"Everyone is done. Please put your onepagers on the table. Please give each other constructive feedback!"

Training exercise: Work out of a onepager.

Tools for the exercise: Empty persona cards, market research documents, and a blank document. Make your own onepager, you can use the informations and the sample onepagers.

You can make your own onepager with te genially APP.

You can use the interactive pictures or infographics in genially : [https://app.genial.ly/
templates/infographics](https://app.genial.ly/templates/infographics)

You have gathered a lot of information about what the problem is, what your business solution is, who the target group is, how big the market is, who the competitors are. Try to visualise all this in a clear, aesthetic one-page document.

Communication skills

Pitch /Mentoring

Communication is the glue that binds human relationships and societies together, and it is as old as humanity itself. As the ages have changed, so have the specific characteristics of communication – but the goal is same: effect for people.

There are many differences between the mentoring of early man and man today, or between a medieval and a modern business or startup situation, but regardless of historical time and place, all can be described by a general model.

Pitch basics, history, and techniques

Basics: In communication, the main roles are played by the sender of the message, the communicator, and the receiver, who receives the message. The content and meaning of the communication is the message. The sender transforms this message into a signal, which reaches the receiver through the information channel. The operation of the transmitter often involves the encoding process. Similarly, the receiver performs the decoding. The communicator transmits the message in some kind of code and the receiver decodes it.

For communication to take place, it is essential that the messages are mutually intelligible to the participants in the process, that they understand the sign systems, symbols and codes used. Communication can only continue in a shared code. The behaviour of the receiver must respond to the signals of the code used within a short time.

A characteristic feature of the transmission process is that things are added to the signal which the communicator did not intend to produce. This noise often originates in the channel of communication. The way in which the message reaches the receiver is the channel of communication. Although not strictly related to the communication model, the communication environment or situation should be mentioned. This includes any external factor or relationship between the communicating parties that has or may have an impact on the communication.

From our point of view, the three most important aspects of communication are.

- Communication in the information-theoretic - cybernetic sense, i.e. information is transmitted in all kinds of systems.
- Communication in technical terms - information is transferred in man-made technical systems (telephones, computers).
- Social communication - information is transferred between people within the social sphere.

Training exercise: The task is to conduct a negotiation based on predefined role cards, where the roles are to represent opposing interests. Based on the role cards, it is not clear which strategy they will have to adopt and they will work on the problem based on their individual characteristics. A good solution is to get to know each other's needs in detail and then it is possible to achieve a win-win outcome. The exercise is known as "Orange Farm" or "Ostrich Eggs" among the general negotiation training exercises.

After the exercise, participants collect their experiences:

- How did the partner behave?
- In what ways was it possible to gather information about his or her efforts (body language, tone of voice, etc.)?
- How important were the small details in our information material?
- What turned the meeting around?
- Who used what soft skills during the discussion?

The observations are collected by the group on flipchart paper and used later in the discussion and to justify the theories in practice.

Tools for the exercise: Make your role cards in genially. You can use the interactive pictures menupoint for this.

History of Pitch

The study of public speaking began about 2,500 years ago in ancient Athens. Men were required to give speeches as part of their civic duties, which included speaking in legislative assembly and at court (sometimes to defend themselves as there were no lawyers for the average Athenian).

Public speaking is therefore almost as old as human culture. Throughout history, public speeches have had political, economic and cultural significance. The pitcher always tries to deliver a message to the audience in a way that is convincing. In the startup ecosystem, the pitch is a tool to gain customers, investors and followers.

Of course, no one expects you to pitch like Steve Jobs or Sam Altman. The purpose of a pitch is to get potential partners to know you. Whether it's employees, customers, investors, a good pitch is necessary to get to know you as a person, as an entrepreneur, to understand your ideas and goals. Only then can you get people on your side who will give their time and energy to build your startup.

A short, clear presentation of your business, idea or project. There are many types of pitch, but this is really the essence of them all. Tell people, in an interesting, memorable, understandable way, what you actually do.

What types of pitches are there?

Pitches can be categorised along two dimensions: type and style

Pitch types

The pitch type is approached as a tool. Who are we actually pitching to? What are we trying to achieve? The type of pitch determines the time available. Pitching is not an exact science, there are many different names and some eleven or so, and we mostly just want to provide a guide and food for thought. The following pitch types will be discussed in ws:

- Elevator pitch

An elevator pitch is a very short, very verbal pitch that explains what the company does, why it is interesting and why it is good for the pitch listener to support the company.

It is usually no more than 2-3 minutes (just enough to say in an elevator), so it should be very focused and only talk about what the listener wants to know right now.

The aim of the pitch is to arouse interest in the startup and to stimulate further conversation, with a minimum waste of time.

- Video pitch (e.g. for a sprint, travel abroad)

Video pitch, as the name suggests, means pitching via online video.

This can be done live or pre-recorded. The duration of the pitch can vary according to the listener's preference, usually between 5 and 10 minutes. It has the advantage of being less time-consuming for the parties involved, no need to travel and, if it is pre-recorded material, the performers can record it several times until it is perfect. The aim of the pitch is to better present the startup to interested parties.

- Investor pitch

An investor pitch is a presentation that is prepared for actively interested investors. This is usually longer, up to 20-30 minutes, and will be followed by a further 20-30 minutes of Q&A. Here, we will really dig deep with the audience. They will be interested in everything you want to talk about and everything you really don't want to talk about. They'll ask tough questions, and they'll also look at how you respond, how patient, honest and enthusiastic you are. Investors don't want to be mean, they want to get to know you and your business inside and out, the good bits and the bad bits. That's why it's OK if you don't know something, if you're facing an unresolved problem or an unmanageable risk. No company is perfect, let alone a startup. The key is honesty and open communication. An investor who is seriously interested in startups will and can help you with these problems, because you will be partners, for better or worse. The aim of the pitch is to present your business to the investor, to get to know you, your team, your successes and your difficulties.

12 distinctive pitch styles

For the sake of completeness, a pitch style or archetype is identified by 12 typical pitch patterns based on Jason Shen's blog - we have highlighted 6 of them.

- The standard pitch

Identify a problem/unmet need within a well-defined market consumer group and create a product or service that solves it within the target group's ability to pay.

How it sounds:

40% of collectors report being dissatisfied or very dissatisfied with their design software. Most in areas X,Y and Z. We have developed a better design software that is twice as good in X, Y and Z as our competitors.

Who should I use?

Many startups. MBA students in business model competitions. Everyone tries at least once to explain startup as a problem-solving set.

What should you use?

It's textbook stuff. It's worth a try if you don't have a better idea. It's dry, clinical, carries no passion, insight or competitive advantage. On the other hand, it's not for nothing that everyone uses it, it's the standard, six-acre foam that is boring in large quantities.

- Traction pitch

There is a product or service that is growing very fast and has a lot of new users, and maybe even a lot of adoption.

How does it sound?

Our app's growth rates have skyrocketed - here's a graph with daily active users. As you can see we have a week on week growth rate of 40% over the last 3 months, this is completely organic, no paid advertising.

When are they used?

This is clearly a very convincing pitch, but it's hard to present it credibly without data to prove it. In the end, almost all investors want to give their money to a project that is growing out of control because they believe there must be something special about the startup. They are aware of how difficult it is to successfully distribute a product/service so quickly without paid publicity.

- X for Y Pitch

The X for Y pitch is a simple way to describe something using the analogy of an established startup. Examples: airbnb for dogs, instagram for video etc. This mostly means taking a proven business model/product/service and transferring it to a new customer segment/market/platform.

How does it sound?

Pokemon is a 24+ billion dollar franchise. Nintendo has absolutely no interest in developing games outside of their core platforms. That's why we made Pokemon for iPhone.

When should I use it?

There are several elements to this pitch that can make it stronger or weaker. First, X should be something that everyone agrees is successful. Often people pitch unvalidated startups on X, which may not work when adapted to Y because the solution X was not workable from the ground up... Y has to be a large, new, penetralhat6 market.

- Personal story pitch

A one-person story about the founders trying to solve a big problem in our lives and creating a product/service that they now want to sell to everyone.

How does it sound?

I built it to solve my own problem. I was very disturbed by having to email myself files all the time, having to keep thumb drives with me, and each machine having a different version of each file. I have made a simple solution that synchronizes my files on different devices and I think a lot of people have found this useful.

When should you use it?

Many founders overuse this pitch. The fact is that most investors don't care about your personal problems. The best customer stories are the ones where the problem is very well subordinated (as in the case of Dropbox) and the product solves a large user problem.

- Painting the future pitch

You embody the future, you can almost see the stunning images of a wonderful new world in front of you. It shows that your company is building the path to the future.

How does it sound?

Isn't it amazing how we always use paper in the office? In 10-15 years, there will be no paper in any office. Paper will be replaced by hardware and software. Our business brings this future one step closer.

When should you use it?

Similar to the evolution pitch, it requires you to be a good storyteller. During the pitch you look further into the future, you see what it will look like decades from now. Once you've convinced investors that this is indeed what will happen, you show that your product is the next logical step towards your vision.

- Wouldn't it be cool if? pitch

You present an interesting idea, something exciting that hasn't been possible before, but thanks to some clever bravery you can make it happen. You get the investor involved in a thought experiment.

How does it sound?

Wouldn't it be nice to have someone to take care of the little things or daily chores for you? Now, with mobile apps, you just post the task and someone will do it for you in 10 minutes.

When should you use it?

The "wouldn't be good" part is the bait. My business can't be built on something that is simply new, but at times it can just be a novelty to introduce my business to an investor. I have to explain how this little thing can become a huge business because it has the potential to be so much more. Think of Twitter in 2006 and Twitter in 2012.

As you can see, there are a lot of different pitches out there. The key is for you to find the ones you need and build your pitches along your own lines so that when you need them, you can pull them out of your back pocket at the right moment.

Below we have included a pitch sample that outlines the main parts of a pitch for a subordinate. Use the parts that we need.

Build your pitch according to what you want to do with it.

The power of storytelling

People like stories. Stories evoke emotions in everyone. Storytelling is an important element of pitch. So it's a good idea to address the audience with a personal story at the beginning of the pitch: if you have the emotional connection, it's easier to absorb the factual information. Therefore, storytelling is the first and most important part of the pitch.

After the storytelling and Pitch sample

- 1) Company/logo
- 2) Vision - Why does your business exist?
- 3) Problem - What do you solve for your customers? What are the problems?
- 4) Your consumers - Who are they and how do you reach them?
- 5) The Solution - What have you built and why is now the right time?
- 6) Your (huge) market - The size of the total market and how to support it
- 7) Your market situation - competitors, macro trends etc. Do you have any insights that others have not found out.
- 8) Current interest - key stats/plans for growth and customer acquisition
- 9) Business model - How to turn upstream into revenue.
- 10) Team - Who are you, where are you from and why will you succeed? Pictures and bios are good, with accurate roles.
- 11) Summary - 3-5 main conclusions (market size, term insight, erdeklodes)
- 12) Financial situation - How much have you already raised and how much more do you need. All financial reports should be included here. Optional a product road map for 6 quarters

Training exercise: make your own pitch deck for a 3 minutes pith. Use the 12 step from the e learning. You can make a visible pitch deck and presentation menupoint inside genially app.

<https://app.genial.ly/templates/presentation>

Each person is asked to pitch for 3 minutes. You have 60 minutes each. Make a video recording, after you can upload this for the genially AI APP, and you van make online meeting with your e-learning participants for feedback.

After the preparation, everyone pitches with camera. If you have the opportunity, you may want to record by phone or tablage. After each pitch, it is a good idea to give feedback to the genially. Feedback aspects should be written on the flipchart board:

1. positive feedback: what was good, what were the strengths of the pitch?
2. what do we think is worth improving? What should we focus on next time?

Pitch and other presentation methods

A special negotiation situation is the pitch, deck or pitch deck, which is a presentation situation, but it is a quasi-negotiation situation, as you want to gain support from either investors or potential buyers.

A **sales pitch** is a condensed sales presentation where a salesperson explains the nature and benefits of their business, ideally in less than one or two minutes. Sales pitches are often referred to as 'elevator pitches' because they should be able to be delivered within the time constraints of a single elevator ride.

Salespeople are past the point of giving prospects hour-long presentations to sell products or services. Nobody has that kind of time and, to be honest, if you need an hour to relay your value proposition, you're doing it wrong.

They're called **elevator pitches** for a reason. Ideally, if you're giving me one, I should be able to understand what you have to offer in the time it takes to get from the lobby to my floor.

A good salesperson should be able to get their message across compellingly and concisely. If you can nail your sales pitch, odds are you'll have more time to talk down the line.

A **product pitch** is not much different than a sales pitch, but is specifically focused on a product or service. You'll go in-depth and emphasize how your product works, how it will solve their pain points, and the specific benefits it will bring to your customers.

As an example, a sales pitch can be broadly focused, like if you're a consulting firm that offers a wide range of services. You're selling your business as a whole, rather than a specific product or service, like a CRM platform or accounting tool.

The Sales Pitch Framework

If you have time to properly expand and work on a conversation, touch on points of interest. Here's a framework you can use for building your elevator pitch:

- **Problem:** Start with a statement or question about the problem you solve. You can present the problem using a personal anecdote, question, or eye-opening statistic. Answer the why.
- **Value Statement:** Share a very clear, concise statement of value. Be action-oriented and outcome focused. Avoid using jargon. Share benefits.
- **How We Do It:** Highlight unique differentiators and explain what you do.
- **Proof Points:** Provide clear reference examples and list recognizable achievements. Share industry validation and awards.
- **Customer Stories:** Share customer examples and successes. Tell emotional and personalized customer stories. Make it real and tangible.
- **Engaging Question:** Close the pitch with an open-ended question, creating a space to have a conversation.

Structure - How to make a sales pitch

- Make it short. - A sales pitch isn't a conventional presentation.
- Make it clear. - This ties in with the previous point. You don't have the time to go on tangents or talk about anything but the message you're trying to get across.
- Explain who your customers are. - Consider the picture you're going to paint in your pitch. Give your listeners perspective on who's buying your product or service.
- Explain the problem they're facing. - Cover why your customer base needs you. Your target market is only as valuable as the problems you can solve for them. Convey a problem they consistently face.
- Explain how your product addresses their needs. - You have to establish why they'd buy from you. What can you do better than your competition?
- Describe what success will look like as a result of using your product. - Show the benefits of your product on a broader scale.

When starting your pitch, you'll want to integrate the following essential elements:

- Start with the problem. Always start with the problem. Unless they know the problem you can solve, they won't be open to hearing how your product is a solution.
- Tailor the start of the pitch to their vertical. No one wants to hear a general pitch that would apply to any business. Research their vertical and use the information you found to personalize the pitch immediately.
- Offer stakes. If they don't solve the problem using your solution, what do they have to lose? You don't need to state it in such clear terms — but alluding to the risks at the start of your pitch can help you secure buy-in straightaway.

Start off a pitch with what you know best — yourself. While I don't think you should focus solely on yourself throughout your entire pitch, starting off with a personal anecdote can help you speak with more authenticity and foster empathy.

Ask a question that relates to the problem you solve.

Start with a stat that resonates and offers stakes. Starting with a stat can be effective — but it has to resonate with the audience and offer stakes.

Training exercise: Participants will work in with genially to develop a presentation of their projects using the pitch methodology. They prepare and present 60-second and 5-minute presentations. The genially member will give specific feedback based on their experience so far. In practice, this means presentations of completed projects, which are also videoed and made available to the teams for future use.

Ideas:

- Tell a story.
- Include a value proposition.
- Personalize the sales pitch.
- Switch up your pitch.
- Practice your pitch.
- Try not to use metaphors.
- Create a WOW moment.
- Appeal to emotions.
- Back it up with facts.
- Tap into their fear of missing out.
- Educate them.

Tools for the exercise: genially/presentations

Mentoring

Mentoring is a most important and special part of every startup ecosystem. Startup ecosystems are characterised by a circularity.

Every business needs to start somewhere. And while you may have the right idea for the product or service around which your fledgling business is based, you may lack knowledge and experience in other areas. This could end up causing you problems. It is important, therefore, to have a source of good information to act as a guiding light for you. A start-up mentor can be very beneficial in this regard.

What is a start-up mento

There is always someone around with knowledge and experience in a particular field who can provide guidance. These people are, in a way, mentors. A start-up mentor is someone who provides mentorship to a start-up business owing to their knowledge and experience with starting and running a business. It can be someone you admire and trust. But if you do not know anybody in the field, you need not worry. You can consult professional start-up mentors over various sessions. Several structured programs are available which include sessions with a mentor.

Why you need a start-up mentor

There are several benefits and advantages that come with having a start-up mentor. Here are a few reasons why you should find a mentor for your start-up:

- **Honest Assessment**A mentor will provide you with an honest assessment of your business and point out what is working and what isn't. Working passionately towards building your business is a good thing, but you run the risk of getting tunnel vision and missing a few crucial pointers here and there.
- **Critical examination**The mentor will attack your idea and plan from every angle to understand its state. This can help reveal aspects of your business and open up avenues you may not have been aware of.
- **Big Picture**Often, working on the little details can make you miss out on the greater vision behind the business and its potential. A mentor can help you take a step back and keep your focus on the right aspects of the job.
- **Opening avenues**As mentioned earlier, a mentor can look at your plan from a different angle. As such, he/she will be able to see potential avenues that you could not, and open up new possibilities for your business.
- **Higher standards**A mentor's experience can be valuable when it comes to assessment of your start-up and he/she will know what to aim for. This will lead to setting higher standards for your business, so it can grow into a trusted brand.
- **Motivation and Patience**A start-up mentor calls upon his/her experience to guide you when you need to be patient with slow growth. Further, it's not uncommon to lose energy and feel de-motivated when the business goes through a lean phase. A mentor can be vital in motivating you.
- **Knowledge and Solutions**A start-up mentor's knowledge can prove very useful in finding the right solutions for any situation that you may face while starting your own business.

- Sounding board Mentors are not going to be available at your beck and call. You should consider them as sounding boards for your ideas. They can be wonderful catalysts for your personal growth.

Mentoring and related soft skills

Mentoring, no matter if we're talking about a 1:1 partnership or a group setting, is a social learning relationship built on trust and respect.

Everything about that description is a soft skill – social implies communication, learning speaks to collaboration and problem-solving, relationship refers to empathy and connectedness, and you can't have trust and respect without equality and open-mindedness.

Collaboration & Problem-Solving

Collaboration and problem-solving in a mentoring relationship is pretty much the same as when working on any project, except that the mentee should take the lead. As a mentor, the key to making the collaboration effective is to encourage your mentee to take responsibility for their learning but engage them where and when it is needed – show them how things are put into practice and provide insight on how to be successful. You can make this even more collaborative by taking this opportunity to join in on the learning and hold each other accountable for the outcomes. If your mentee hits a rough patch, remember that problem-solving doesn't mean doing the work for them, so resist the urge to "save" your mentee. Pull out those stellar listening and questioning skills and guide them towards figuring out a solution for themselves, which will be more a more meaningful and lasting learning opportunity for your mentee.

Empathy & Connectedness

Empathy and connectedness can be a tricky fence to balance. While you don't want to be overly familiar with your mentee or make them feel like you're hovering, you also don't want to be so unapproachable that your mentee feels hesitant about being open and honest with you. This is one of those topics that should be discussed at the beginning of the relationship and speaks to a high level of empathy in itself. Ask your mentee about topics of conversation that are off limits, if they are they comfortable with a casual relationship or if they prefer things to stay very professional, etc. Also clarify expectations around staying connected. Does your mentee want to receive information or emails from you between meetings or do they prefer to keep things within the confines of your meeting times? Another aspect of connectedness is finding out if your mentee is comfortable having you assist with introductions to additional people who may be helpful to their development. Even though most mentees would welcome that, don't assume! The most important thing is to be savvy enough to provide your mentee with an environment that is safe and conducive to learning.

Equality & Open-Mindedness

One of the most challenging aspects of growing into an effective mentoring relationship is the development of trust between the mentor and mentee. Equality and open-mindedness are invaluable qualities that will help overcome some of the awkward power dynamics that can naturally occur when people who are at different stages in their careers begin to work together. A great way to lessen the gap between your levels of seniority is to share a mentoring skill that you've been working on as a development opportunity and to sincerely ask your mentee for feedback. By sharing that you too are still learning, it shows your mentee that you're in this process together and you can learn from one another.

Open-mindedness comes into play as you look for ways to support your mentee's development efforts with purpose but without judgement and to find ways to promote the successes of your mentee.

As a mentee

In a nutshell, mentoring relationships help people improve their soft skills like listening, receiving feedback, and empathy because they use those same skills within the relationships themselves. People can practice those skills within the context of the mentoring relationships, even if the main focus of the relationship is not centered on the soft skill itself.

1. Communication Skills

Mentoring relationships allow people to share their feelings about different topics at hand or other critical aspects of the mentoring relationship, creating a safe place to explore and express emotions. These relationships also encourage discussion through open-ended questions that require more descriptive answers than just yes or no, which in turn makes people dive deeper into their own thoughts, feelings, and opinions. Try this yourself by asking open-ended questions of your mentoring partner and by probing into some of the opinions and feelings being expressed.

2. Listening Skills

Mentoring relationships rely heavily on good listening skills. People need to listen for what is being said, but also for what is not being said. This can lead to learning opportunities, breakthroughs, and moments of personal and professional growth. To try this yourself, focus on the thoughts, ideas, and feelings being communicated by your mentoring partner. Really try to be present for them and concentrate on what your partner is trying to convey instead of preparing your response.

3. Empathy

Good mentoring relationships help people build empathy, often by **forging a bond** and connection between partners that helps them learn how to put themselves in one another's situation and imagine how they would feel and react. As people practice and build this skill within the safety of a mentoring relationship, they can then begin to apply it in other work situations. In fact, empathy can be used to build better communication and listening skills.

Training exercise: Participants will work in pairs with ChatGPT, as a mentor-mentee. This is a rapid mentoring method. Everybody have 5 minute, to try a mentoring process with AI. One person play a mentee, the AI play a mentor. After the 5 minute the human -AI pairs make a switch. make a notes about your experiences

Tools for the exercise: chatGPT account, smart phone or laptop

AI as a mentor

One of today's hottest technologies is AI. It's increasingly being adopted in marketing, copywriting and even real estate. The question arises, is there a place for this technological innovation in mentoring? To answer this question, we need to be aware that today's AI technologies do not replace humans, but help them: for example, they shorten certain workflows. Thus, it cannot replace the mentor, but it can help both the mentor and the mentee in their work, for example in preparing for mentoring sessions. One of the best known AI applications today is ChatGPT, which can be used to ask general questions about startups. This can be an effective help in the early stage phase, but it will not replace the personal experience and pedagogical sense of the mentor. AI can therefore be used in mentoring, but it is not a substitute for a human being in the process.

Training Exercise: During the simulation exercise, we will activate a ChatGPT account. Make a conversation with AI: what is your first question about startup, startup ecosystem? Try the ChatGPT limits!

Tools for the exercise: smart phone or laptop

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